

Development of High Power K/Ka-Band Helix TWT

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Abstract: *A helix TWT having unprecedented power across the full K/Ka band (18-40 GHz) has been developed. This TWT has a minimum CW output power greater than 130 W over the full band and greater than 200 W for most of the band (19 to 38 GHz). This K/Ka band helix TWT development has leveraged the underlying technology from L-3 ETI's high-power millimeter-wave helix TWTs that were developed over the last several years for communications and instrumentation applications. Modern design codes that have been specifically developed for vacuum electronics devices by NRL / SAIC, notably CHRISTINE-3D and MICHELLE-3D were critical to the successful development of this high power-bandwidth product K/Ka-band helix TWT. .*

Keywords: Traveling-wave tube; RF amplifier; octave bandwidth

Introduction

Over the last several years, the continuous-wave (CW) and average output power capability of millimeter-wave helix TWTs at L-3 Electron Technologies, Inc. (ETI) has increased by a factor of two at Ka-band frequencies from 250 W (2004) to 500 W (2008); and at Q-band frequencies from 120W (2000) to 230 W (2004) [1]. This remarkable output power increase has been in large part driven by the ever increasing demand in high-data-rate communications for both commercial and military platforms. By taking advantage of the improvements achieved in the millimeter-wave power handling capability from the aforementioned TWTs, L-3 ETI has successfully developed wideband helix TWTs covering 18 to 40 GHz either in two TWTs, or in a single TWT. In 2006 and 2007, as a first step, L-3 ETI developed two 1.5:1 bandwidth helix TWTs: 1) the 8928H, a 150-W K-band (18.0 – 26.5 GHz) helix TWT; and 2) the 8929H, a 150-W Ka-band (26.5 – 40.0 GHz) helix TWT. The saturated performance of the 8928H and the 8929H are shown in Fig. 1. The output power is greater than 150 W for each TWT across 18 – 26.5 GHz for the former and across 26.5 – 40 GHz for the latter. The output power ranges from 160 W to 250 W, and overall efficiency ranges from 33% to 50% for the helix TWTs with a two-stage depressed collector. Excellent focusing is demonstrated with the intercepted current less than 0.7% of the cathode current for the two units shown. The 8928H and the 8929H are currently in production, available for instrumentation applications.

L-3 ETI and the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) started the development of the 8927H in 2007 with a goal of 120 W minimum output power across 18 – 40 GHz. The steady increase of the power-bandwidth product figure-of-merit, $P_{avg} f_0 \Delta f$, over the last 15 years for millimeter-wave helix TWTs at L-3 ETI is shown in Fig. 2. The 8927H that provides 130 W minimum output power across 18 – 40 GHz (200 W average power over the bandwidth) extends the power-bandwidth product from that of the 8929H which had the highest power-bandwidth product before the 8927H was developed. The performance of this state-of-the-art K/Ka band (18 – 40 GHz) amplifier will be discussed in this paper.

18 – 40 GHz Helix TWT Development

The 8927H K/Ka band helix TWT development started with a goal of maximizing CW output power across the full 18 - 40 GHz. Initial estimates from modeling and previous experience suggested that at least 120 W was achievable, a level that would increase the highest reported power-bandwidth product in that frequency range. In the course of the development, four circuit design iterations were built and tested. The successive design iterations improved performance and/or addressed anomalies observed from the prior designs.

Engineering Models 1 - 3: The first engineering model (EM001) succeeded in demonstrating CW output power greater than 120 W across 18 – 40 GHz with good thermal stability. However, EM001 also exhibited a broad output power dip of approximately 2 dB over 6 GHz, centered around 29 GHz. Extensive testing and modeling resulted in a second engineering model (EM002) designed to eliminate the power dip. The mid-band power dip was successfully eliminated, but the output power of EM002 was overall lower than the predicted level by approximately 1 to 2 dB over the bandwidth. This output power discrepancy was later determined to be caused by a manufacturing error. The third engineering model (EM003) corrected the identified manufacturing error, but maintained the basic circuit design of the EM002 that removed the power dip observed in EM001. The EM003 RF performance is shown in Fig. 3. Although the output power is greater than 200 W over most of the bandwidth, it decreases significantly at frequencies below 20 GHz and drops to 75 W (48.8 dBm) at 18 GHz. EM003 also has approximately 30 dB gain variation over the full 18 – 40 GHz bandwidth, but this variation can be reduced with an equalizer if needed.

The CHRISTINE-3D-simulated output power and gain shown in Fig. 3 are in excellent agreement with the measured values. The measured and simulated body-intercepted current (I_w) responses, normalized to the cathode current (I_k), are also shown in Fig. 3. The accuracy of the modeling and simulation tools and the insight they provide, as exemplified here by CHRISTINE-3D [2] in modeling the beam-wave dynamics, have been critical to understanding the behavior of the TWT. In particular, testing and modeling revealed the steep decrease in the output power of EM003 at the low end of the bandwidth to be due to high second harmonic output power that competes with the fundamental interaction.

Engineering Model 4: The circuit design was modified in the fourth engineering model (EM004) to improve the output power at the low end of the 18 – 40 GHz frequency range by reducing the harmonic output power compared to the EM003 design. The saturated performance of the EM004 circuit is shown in Fig. 4, exhibiting output power greater than 135 W across the full bandwidth and greater than 200 W from 19 to 38 GHz. Also shown are CHRISTINE-3D power and gain, and MICHELLE-3D [3] overall efficiency predictions with a three-stage collector compared to the measured performance.

Conclusion

The 8927H developed by L-3 ETI and NRL demonstrates output power greater than 130 W across the full K/Ka band (18 – 40 GHz) and greater than 200 W across 19 – 38 GHz. The accurate modeling codes developed by NRL / SAIC were instrumental in the successful development of this state-of-the-art wideband millimeter wave amplifier.

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Figure 1. Measured saturated performance and helix body current for both the 18 – 26.5 GHz and the 26.5 – 40 GHz TWT (8928H and 8929H, respectively).

Figure 2. Power-bandwidth product evolution for high-power millimeter-wave helix TWTs at L-3 ETI.

Figure 3. Measured and modeled output power, gain and helix body current for the 8927H EM003. Each point is individually saturated.

Figure 4. Measured and modeled output power, gain and overall efficiency for the 8927H EM004. Each point is individually saturated.

References

- [1] C. K. Chong et al., *IEEE Trans. Plasma Science*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 1227-1238, June 2010.
- [2] D. Chernin et al. *IEEE Trans. On Electron Devices*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 3-11, January 2001
- [3] J. Petillo et al. *IEEE Trans. Plasma Sci.*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp.1238-1264, June 2002.